

Cyclic voltammetric investigations of copper(II)-chloro and -bromo complexes in aqueous medium

Jagdish Prasad*, E. J. Ukpong and Krishna Srivastava

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, India

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The electrochemical behavior of copper(II)-chloro and -bromo complex species has been studied in different concentrations of chloride and bromide ions in aqueous solutions by means of cyclic voltammetry. The cyclic voltammetric parameters are calculated. Both the complex species involve two redox steps. The first couple ($\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$) involves a single-electron, diffusion-controlled quasi-reversible electrode process (EC mechanism), while the second step involves irreversible reduction of Cu(I)-halide species to metallic copper. Also, the reduction potential for the first couple (E_{pc_1}) becomes more positive and that of the second step (E_{pc_2}) becomes more negative with increasing concentration of chloride/bromide ions.

Copper(II)-chloro complexes, which absorb in the uv and visible regions (λ_{max} ~250 and 800 nm), have mainly been investigated by spectrophotometric methods in aqueous solutions. Comparison of stability constants of the chloro and bromo complexes for both copper(II) and copper(I) in organo solvents¹ with the corresponding constants in water² illustrates the importance of solvents in complex ion stability. The effects of halide ion concentration and/or solvent in the formation of complex species and their stabilities have led to considerable interest in the chemistry of non-aqueous copper-halide solutions. Copper(II/I) electron-transfer reactions are currently of interest because the structural differences between the two oxidation states place unusual constraints on the electron-transfer kinetics³. Here we report a detailed electrochemical redox behavior of copper(II)-

chloro and -bromo complex species over a wide range of halide ion (Cl^- and Br^-) concentrations (0.1 to 3.0 M) in aqueous solutions.

Results and discussion

The electrochemical behavior of 1 mM aqueous solution each of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CuBr}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ at various concentrations of KCl and KBr (0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 and 3.0 M) was preliminarily investigated in deaerated aqueous medium at glassy carbon electrode (GCE) by means of cyclic voltammetry (CV) with scan rates (ν) ranging from 10 to 300 mV s^{-1} . CV parameters for CuCl_2/KCl and CuBr_2/KBr systems at 1.0 M concentration of chloride and bromide ions at different scan rates are given in Tables 1 and 3, while Tables 2 and 4 list the cyclic voltammetric param-

Table 1. Cyclic voltammetric parameters for 1 mM $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in aqueous 1.0 M KCl

Scan rate mV s^{-1}	First step							Second step			
	E_{pc_1} mV	E_{pa_1} mV	I_{pc_1} μA	I_{pa_1} μA	$E^{0'}$ mV	ΔE_p mV	I_{pa_1}/I_{pc_1}	E_{pc_2} mV	E_{pa_2} mV	I_{pc_2} μA	I_{pa_2} μA
10	+190	+260	8.0	6.5	+225	70	0.81	-390	-160	12.5	55.0
25	+185	+255	12.0	10.0	+220	70	0.83	-420	-160	15.5	60.0
50	+180	+255	17.5	14.0	+218	75	0.80	-425	-170	21.0	77.0
100	+180	+265	23.5	19.5	+223	85	0.83	-430	-160	27.0	99.0
150	+180	+265	29.5	23.5	+223	85	0.83	-465	-160	29.0	112.0
200	+175	+265	34.0	27.5	+220	90	0.80	-480	-165	33.5	125.0
250	+165	+270	38.0	31.0	+218	105	0.81	-500	-165	37.0	134.0
300	+165	+270	42.0	34.0	+218	105	0.81	-	-	-	-

$$E^{0'} = \frac{E_{pa} + E_{pc}}{2}$$

Table 2. Cyclic voltammetric parameters for 1 mM CuCl₂·2H₂O in various aqueous chloride ion concentrations at $\nu = 25 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$

[KCl] <i>M</i>	First step							Second step			
	E_{pc_1} mV	E_{pa_1} mV	I_{pc_1} μA	I_{pa_1} μA	$E^{0'}$ mV	ΔE_p mV	I_{pa_1} I_{pc_1}	E_{pc_2} mV	E_{pa_2} mV	I_{pc_2} μA	I_{pa_2} μA
0.1	+90	+180	13.0	11.0	+135	90	0.84	-310	-70	14.5	40.0
0.2	+125	+200	13.0	10.0	+162	75	0.77	-330	-105	15.5	45.0
0.5	+165	+230	13.0	10.0	+198	65	0.77	-410	-150	15.0	39.0
1.0	+185	+255	12.0	10.0	+220	70	0.83	-420	-160	15.5	60.0
1.5	+215	+290	12.0	10.0	+252	75	0.83	-435	-190	14.5	65.0
2.0	+225	+300	12.0	10.0	+262	75	0.83	-450	-200	17.0	-
3.0	+240	+325	6.5	6.0	+283	85	0.92	-505	-250	8.5	-

Table 3. Cyclic voltammetric parameters for 1 mM CuBr₂·H₂O in aqueous 1.0 M KBr

Scan rate mV s^{-1}	First step							Second step			
	E_{pc_1} mV	E_{pa_1} mV	I_{pc_1} μA	I_{pa_1} μA	$E^{0'}$ mV	ΔE_p mV	I_{pa_1} I_{pc_1}	E_{pc_2} mV	E_{pa_2} mV	I_{pc_2} μA	I_{pa_2} μA
10	+225	+295	7.5	6.0	+260	70	0.86	-435	-190	10.0	48.0
25	+215	+295	11.5	10.0	+255	80	0.83	-460	-180	14.0	65.5
50	+215	+300	17.0	14.0	+258	85	0.82	-470	-180	18.5	82.5
100	+210	+310	24.0	19.5	+258	95	0.81	-490	-170	26.0	104.5
150	+200	+310	29.0	24.0	+255	110	0.83	-515	-165	31.5	117.0
200	+195	+315	33.0	27.5	+255	120	0.83	-535	-165	36.0	130.0
250	+190	+315	37.5	31.5	+253	125	0.83	-540	-160	40.0	-
300	+185	+320	40.0	33.5	+254	135	0.84	-545	-160	43.5	-

Table 4. Cyclic voltammetric parameters for 1 mM CuBr₂·H₂O in various aqueous bromide ion concentrations at $\nu = 25 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$

[KBr] <i>M</i>	First step							Second step			
	E_{pc_1} mV	E_{pa_1} mV	I_{pc_1} μA	I_{pa_1} μA	$E^{0'}$ mV	ΔE_p mV	I_{pa_1} I_{pc_1}	E_{pc_2} mV	E_{pa_2} mV	I_{pc_2} μA	I_{pa_2} μA
0.1	+110	+175	12.5	9.5	+143	65	0.76	-360	-55	13.5	68.0
0.2	+140	+210	12.5	10.0	+180	70	0.80	-390	-90	14.0	50.0
0.5	+175	+250	12.5	10.0	+213	75	0.80	-420	-140	14.5	58.0
1.0	+215	+295	11.5	10.0	+255	80	0.83	-460	-180	14.0	65.5
1.5	+250	+330	11.5	9.2	+290	80	0.80	-485	-230	15.0	71.0
2.0	+270	+350	11.0	9.0	+310	80	0.82	-520	-260	15.0	-
3.0	+325	+420	7.5	7.0	+373	85	0.93	-555	-300	11.0	-

eters at different concentrations of chloride and bromide ions, respectively, at $\nu = 25 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$. Fig. 1 displays the cyclic voltammogram of 1 mM CuCl₂·2H₂O in aqueous 3.0 M KCl.

One reduction peak (c_1) appears on the negative-going forward potential sweep in the potential range from +0.70 to -0.20 V vs SCE, with a directly associated reoxidation peak (a_1) in the reverse scan (Fig. 1). Controlled potential

coulometry at -0.10 V vs SCE indicates that this reduction process involves the consumption of one electron per molecule of copper(II)-halo species. Further, both the chloro- and bromo-copper(II) complexes exhibit a second cathodic peak (c_2), attributable to the Cu^{+/0} redox change, on the negative-going potential scan in the potential region +0.70 to -0.65 V vs SCE lacking a directly associated response in the reverse scan because of the rapid demetallation follow-

Fig. 1. CV of 1 mM $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in aqueous 3.0 M KCl at scan rate 25 mV s^{-1}

ing this second electron transfer. This is confirmed by the appearance of the characteristic anodic stripping peak (a_2) in the reverse scan due to the reoxidation of electrodeposited copper metal to free Cu^1 ions as shown in Fig. 1.

Analysis of the cyclic voltammetric responses for the $\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$ couple with scan rates ranging from 10 to 300 mV s^{-1} at various concentrations of chloride ions showed the following features. The anodic to cathodic peak current ratio, I_{pa1}/I_{pc1} is less than 1.0, indicating that the electron transfer is followed by a chemical reaction (EC mechanism). Both the cathodic peaks (E_{pc1} and E_{pc2}) corresponding to $\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$ and $\text{Cu}^{+/0}$ changes shift cathodically with increasing scan rate (Tables 1 and 3). Also, the value of ΔE_p ($= E_{pa1} - E_{pc1}$) progressively increases with increasing scan rate (from 80 to 160, 65 to 110, 70 to 130, 70 to 105, 65 to 125, 85 to 140 and 80 to 145 mV in 0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 and 3.0 M KCl, respectively). Both these observations are indicative of the heterogeneous quasi-reversible one-electron transfer process⁴⁻⁶. The parameter ΔE_p can be assumed as a rough index of the degree of departure from electrochemical reversibility, considering that for a purely reversible one-electron charge transfer, ΔE_p is expected⁴ to be 59 mV. The plot of the cathodic peak current or anodic peak current (I_{pc1} or I_{pa1}) vs the square-root of scan rate ($\nu^{1/2}$) gives a straight-line passing through origin, showing that the electrode process is diffusion-controlled⁴. However, plot of I_{pc2} vs $\nu^{1/2}$

is linear with positive intercept, indicating that the electrode process at the second step is not fully diffusion-controlled. Similar observations are also noted for $\text{CuBr}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in all KBr concentrations studied.

A perusal of Table 2 shows that the cathodic peak potential (E_{pc1}) becomes more positive while E_{pc2} becomes more negative with increasing concentration of chloride ions. This behavior clearly indicates that the higher oxidation state copper(II)-chloro complex species becomes more destabilized with respect to copper(I)-chloro complex species with increasing chloride ion concentration. It is relevant to mention that the cathodic and anodic currents (I_{pc1} , I_{pa2} and I_{pc2}) are significantly smaller at 3.0 M KCl as compared to those at lower concentration of chloride ions (Table 2), clearly indicating some major change in the nature of the Cu^{II} -chloro species. This may probably be due to the formation of tetrahedral complex species, CuCl_4^{2-} . It has been reported² earlier that only mononuclear complex species, $\text{CuCl}_{\text{aq}}^+$, $\text{CuCl}_{2\text{aq}}$, $\text{CuCl}_{3\text{aq}}^-$ and CuCl_4^{2-} exist in aqueous solution depending upon the chloride ion concentration. The first three tetragonally distorted octahedral species have only one absorption band in the uv region, respectively situated at 250 nm (40000 cm^{-1}) for $\text{CuCl}_{\text{aq}}^+$ and $\text{CuCl}_{2\text{aq}}$ when the chloride ion concentration is less than 1.0 M, and at 270 nm (37000 cm^{-1}) for $\text{CuCl}_{3\text{aq}}^-$ at chloride ion concentration 1.0 to 2.0 M. On the other hand, tetrahedral CuCl_4^{2-} species has three absorption peaks at 240 (41700), 265–270 (37400 – 37000) and 370–380 nm (27000 – 26300 cm^{-1}) at chloride ion concentration $>2.5 \text{ M}$. It may, therefore, be concluded that the shift of the cathodic peak potential (E_{pc1}) of the first couple, $\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$ towards more positive potential (Table 2) with increasing concentration of chloride ion may be due to successive formation of the copper(II)-chloro complex species as described above.

Further, a comparison of peak currents I_{pc1} and I_{pc2} at a given scan rate and a given chloride ion concentration (Tables 2 and 4) shows that $I_{pc2} > I_{pc1}$, though both the reduction steps involve one-electron transfer. This may be due to weak adsorption of reduced Cu^1 -chloro complex species at the surface of the working electrode (GCE) and/or due to change in coordination number/geometry^{3,7} of the Cu^1 species. Examples of small molecules coordination number invariant $\text{Cu}^{\text{II/I}}$ couples are rare. Even more rare are those that are conformationally invariant⁷.

Experimental

$\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CuBr}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, KCl and KBr used were of A.R. grade. Fresh solutions were prepared in double-distilled water before recording the cyclic voltammograms.

Cyclic voltammetry was carried out with a BAS CV-IB instrument having an electrochemical cell with a three-electrode system. The working electrode was a glassy carbon electrode (GCE), platinum wire was used as an auxiliary electrode, and saturated calomel electrode as a reference electrode ($E^\circ = +0.242$ V vs NHE). Coulometric measurement was performed with BAS CV-27.

All the cyclic voltammetry experiments were done in an inert atmosphere achieved by purging the cell solution with extra pure nitrogen for 15 min. An inert atmosphere of nitrogen was also maintained over the cell solution during recording of the voltammograms. All the experiments were performed at 25°.

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